

Rethinking Value with Modern Monetary Theory: Toward a Reconstruction of Economics through Dynamic Approach

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Abstract

This paper takes an initial step toward reconstructing a theory of value consistent with Modern Monetary Theory, offering an alternative to the utility theory of value. By analyzing the arguments of its proponents, we confirm that the currently dominant utility theory of value relies on static models and assumes the existence of “moments in which all exchanges are completed simultaneously.” The unrealistic nature of this assumption has rarely been questioned; however, it not only impedes the proper integration of money into the theoretical framework but also leads to significant differences in the conclusions of exchange theory. In response, this paper proposes a new theory of value that incorporates a dynamic aspect, explicitly reflecting the characteristics of a market economy in which exchanges occur continuously. Furthermore, within the framework of this new value theory, we propose *marginal expected utility analysis* that extends the conventional marginal utility analysis into a dynamic setting. We examine its applicability to the real economy through both a commodity market model and a government-issued public money model. The results are broadly consistent with the claims of Modern Monetary Theory and Post-Keynesian economics, including markup pricing theory and the tax-driven money view. Moreover, by modeling firms as price-setters rather than price-takers, we theoretically derive realistic price-adjustment processes in disequilibrium markets without relying on ad hoc assumptions. These findings indicate that accurately capturing the dynamics of continuous market exchanges is essential for reconstructing the theory of value and exchange.

Keywords: Theory of Value, Modern Monetary Theory, Tax-Driven Money View, Markup-Pricing Theory.

1 Introduction

The theory of value has long been absent from the forefront of economic discourse. Yet, at one time, it was among the most controversial topics, shaping the distinctions between different schools of thought. After World War II, economic thoughts were classified into three main strands: neoclassical economics, which advocates the utility theory of value (UTV); Marxian economics, which addresses the (surplus) labor theory of value (LTV); and Keynesian economics, which does not have its own value theory. However, Keynesian economics gradually declined after it failed to explain the stagflation of the 1970s and 1980s and was criticized by Lucas for the lack of microfoundation (Lucas 1976). In addition, the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991 led to a severe decline in Marxian economics, causing LTV to fade from prominence.

Against this background, neoclassical economics established a dominant position, and UTV came to be widely accepted as the de facto standard. The overwhelming dominance of neoclassical economics (or mainstream economics) has persisted for decades. However, the global financial crisis of 2008 undermined confidence in mainstream macroeconomics, thereby renewing interest in heterodox economics. In particular, since the 2010s, Modern

Monetary Theory (MMT), presenting itself as a new economic paradigm, has gained prominence (Mitchell, Wray, and Watts 2019; Wray 2024; Kelton 2020). The emergence of MMT generated significant controversy with the mainstream economists (Drumetz and Pfister 2021; Tymoigne and Wray 2013). Much of the debate concerns the government's ability to sustain fiscal deficits; yet, the positions of the two schools contradict each other in nearly every aspect (Ehnts 2022, p. 3). Because of these fundamental differences, their arguments often fail to converge, sometimes resulting in emotional disputes.

Whereas the differences in value theory were the main point of contention between schools of thought in the past, the differences in monetary view have increasingly come to define their distinguishing lines in recent years. The commodity theory of money, on which mainstream relies, explains the origin of money as follows. Humankind initially engaged in economic activities based on barter. However, in order to resolve the problem of the *double coincidence of wants* (Jevons 1876, p. 14), goods widely recognized as valuable—such as shells, grains, or precious metals—came to be used as a medium of exchange, and money thus emerged spontaneously. Nevertheless, despite extensive research in sociology, little evidence has been found to support the orthodox commodity theory of money, which posits that money arose naturally from a barter economy (Martin 2014 [2013]; Graeber 2016 [2011]). Moreover, following the complete abolition of the gold standard in the 1971 Nixon Shock, fiat money has continued to circulate despite lacking any intrinsic value. This phenomenon is difficult to account for within the commodity theory of money, which attributes the acceptability of money to its intrinsic value. By contrast, MMT addresses neo-chartalism, which combines the state theory of money and the credit theory of money. Neo-chartalism argues that the state's tax system and private credit system have played a central role in the emergence and evolution of money, and that this view is supported by a broader range of historical and anthropological evidence than the orthodox view—money originated from barter. According to neo-chartalism, money is accepted in commercial transactions because it can be used to discharge tax obligations to the state, thereby offering a natural explanation for the circulation of fiat money.

Thus, the proponents of MMT assert the superiority of its monetary theory; however, MMT contains a theoretical gap regarding value theory. Mainstream economics possesses a solid foundation in microeconomics involving marginal utility theory and equilibrium price theory. In contrast, MMT does not incorporate these theories into its framework and develops its own macroeconomic theory without establishing its value theory. This feature can also be found in Post-Keynesian economics, which is often regarded as the 'precursor' of MMT. Whereas mainstream economics constructs its macroeconomic theory upon a microeconomic foundation—an approach commonly known as *microfoundation*—economists of Post-Keynesian and MMT generally reject this approach so as to avoid the *fallacy of composition*. For this reason, compared with mainstream economics, MMT lacks coverage in areas of microeconomics, including value theory.

While MMT lacks its value theory, it does include several discussions on prices. Within the MMT framework of price determination, the overall price level is regulated by two primary dynamics (Mosler 2023, p. 89). First, the exchange ratio between money and the *numeraire*

is determined through its receipt via fiscal spending by the government. Subsequently, the prices of other goods are adjusted secondarily through market mechanisms. Labor is the most suitable candidate for the role of the *numeraire* in terms of price stability because labor is a production factor common to nearly all goods, and by setting wages, the government can effectively control the overall price level in the markets.

However, the MMT explanation of price theory is largely articulated in natural language and, compared to mainstream price theory, lacks mathematical rigor. There are limited studies that mathematically formulate the price-determination mechanism in MMT. One example is the study by Tcherneva (Tcherneva 2002); however, the represented model assumes a simplified economy with only a single type of good, and it does not capture the process by which goods other than the *numeraire* are secondarily adjusted according to the market mechanism, as described above. Seemingly, a comprehensive mathematical model representing MMT's price theory has yet to be established.

The lack of formalization in MMT is not limited to price theory; rather, it reflects an overall tendency in MMT literature. One possible reason for this is the absence of a coherent value theory. In contrast, mainstream economics begins with UTV based on the assumption of utility-maximizing individuals and has developed mathematically rigorous economic theories from this foundation. Setting aside its explanatory power in practice, this approach has achieved a certain degree of success in constructing a coherent theoretical framework, which underpins its current dominant position.

The absence of a theory of value stands as an obstacle to the further theoretical development of MMT. This paper aims to explore a theory of value consistent with MMT, and to provide a foundation for reconstructing its theoretical framework. In addition, by presenting a new theory of value capable of serving as an alternative to UTV, the paper seeks to clarify the structure of conflict between mainstream and MMT.

2 Static Nature of Utility Value Theory

This section provides a detailed critical analysis of the contemporary UTV which is adopted by mainstream economics. It outlines the arguments of prominent economists such as Jevons, Walras and Debreu, who contributed to the development of UTV and market equilibrium theory. Jevons's argument is analyzed in greater detail here, as it will be referred to as the starting point for the construction of a new value theory in the consequent section. UTV provides an exchange theory based on rational behavior of agents, serving as a theoretical foundation of mainstream economics. However, the theory was developed on the basis of a timeless, static model, and was not originally intended for application to dynamic economic analysis. Although this limitation is rarely emphasized, it poses serious problems when applying UTV to practical purposes, particularly with respect to the treatment of money.

2.1 Marginal Utility Theory by Jevons

One of the key figures of the Marginal Revolution, William S. Jevons argued that the relative value of a commodity is determined by the ratio of the utility it provides, thereby criticizing the conventional LTV. During his era, the notion of utility-maximizing individuals had not yet emerged in the sphere of political economy. In his seminal work, "The theory of Political Economy," Jevons refers to Jeremy Bentham, introducing the following definition of "utility":

By utility is meant that property in any object, whereby it tends to produce benefit, advantage, pleasure, good, or happiness (all this, in the present case, comes to the same thing), or (what comes again to the same thing) to prevent the happening of mischief, pain, evil, or unhappiness to the party whose interest is considered. (Jevons 1888, p. 46)

Jevons recognized the difficulty in quantifying the intensity of pleasure and pain experienced by individuals. Nevertheless, he asserted that the magnitude of utility can be externally inferred through observable human behavior, thereby allowing for the numerical treatment of a commodity's utility (Jevons 1888, p. 33). Suppose an individual is offered two commodities, A and B, and is able to choose one of them for free. By observing the choice made, the relative utilities of the two commodities for that individual can be estimated.

On the assumption of utility-maximizing individuals, Jevons analyzed a single-market model with two commodities. He demonstrated that, in market equilibrium, the exchange ratio between the two commodities is equal to the ratio of their marginal utilities (MU). His argument can be summarized in the following two statements.

- (i) In a state of market disequilibrium, price adjustments occur towards equilibrium.
- (ii) In a state of market equilibrium, the exchange ratio between the two commodities is determined by the ratio of their MU.

In what follows, we examine the derivation process. Jevons's analysis is based on the following assumptions:

- The entire group of market participants who initially endowed with commodity A is represented by a trading body, X. Similarly, the group of participants who initially endowed with commodity B is represented by a trading body, Y.
- Commodities of the same type are regarded as homogeneous, and the law of one price holds.
- By the law of diminishing marginal utility, the MU of a commodity initially endowed to the agent increases as it is exchanged away, while the MU of a commodity obtained from the market decreases as transactions proceed.

Figure 1: Marginal utility of commodities according to the number of transactions

Assuming that the two commodities are traded at a fixed exchange ratio, the relationship between the quantity traded and the MU can be depicted as shown in Figure 1:

The vertical axis measures the utility of a commodity per unit of exchange, while the horizontal axis represents the number of transactions. At the outset, the MU of the commodity acquired exceeds that of the commodity relinquished, so X and Y are initially willing to exchange. As the transaction continues, the gap between the MU of the commodity relinquished and that of the commodity acquired gradually narrows. When the MU of the two commodities become equal, at the intersection of the two curves, the individual is no longer willing to trade.

We now return to the initial assumption that the exchange ratio is fixed. If the exchange ratio is chosen arbitrarily, the quantity that X is willing to trade does not necessarily match the quantity that Y is willing to trade. Suppose that X stops trading first: in this case, Y may still wish to continue trading but cannot find a counterpart. This situation is called a state of disequilibrium. Under such circumstances, Y has an incentive to sell at a slightly lower price than the given exchange rate in order to secure more trading partners. This is because, even if Y must accept a slightly less favorable exchange ratio, increasing the transactions until a satisfactory level is reached will provide greater utility in total. Through such price adjustments, the gap between the quantities that X and Y wish to trade gradually narrows (see Figure 2). This explains the market adjustment mechanism described in Statement (i).

Statement (ii) can be derived as follows. If the market is in equilibrium, neither party has an incentive to change prices, and the current number of transactions must correspond to the quantities that both X and Y wish to trade. In other words, at the current transaction level, the MU of commodities A and B are equal from the perspectives of both X and Y. Therefore, the exchange ratio of commodities A and B must correspond to the ratio of their MU from the perspective of both market participants.

It is important to note that Jevons's analysis is based on a static model. In his definition of utility, only the direct benefits derived from the commodities—commonly called "use value"—are considered, and the potential for exchanging these commodities with others in the future is entirely ignored. Moreover, in his single-market model, economic agents

Figure 2: Mechanism of market price adjustment

are assumed to behave rationally so as to maximize their utility after all transactions are completed. Taken together, this implies an underlying assumption that, by the end of the period, all commodities are consumed by their owners. In other words, agents cannot carry their possessions over to the next period for future exchange. Jevons himself explicitly cautioned against this point:

We must carefully distinguish, at the same time, between the Statics and Dynamics of this subject. The real condition of industry is one of perpetual motion and change. Commodities are being continually manufactured and exchanged and consumed. If we wished to have a complete solution of the problem in all its natural complexity, we should have to treat it as a problem of motion—a problem of dynamics. But it would surely be absurd to attempt the more difficult question when the more easy one is yet so imperfectly within our power. It is only as a purely statical problem that I can venture to treat the action of exchange. Holders of commodities will be regarded not as continuously passing on these commodities in streams of trade, but as possessing certain fixed amounts which they exchange until they come to equilibrium. (Jevons 1888, p. 78)

In summary, Jevons explicitly acknowledged that his model abstracts from the temporal continuity of market transactions, treating all exchanges as if they were conducted instantaneously. Despite recognizing the necessity of dynamic analysis, technical limitations compelled him to focus on static analysis.

2.2 General Equilibrium Model by Walras

Shortly after Jevons's publication, Leon Walras proposed a theory of price determination across multiple markets in his book *Éléments d'économie politique pure* (Elements of Pure Economics) (Walras 1983 [1874]). This framework, now referred to as general equilibrium theory, laid the foundation for later developments in mathematical economics. In his model, each economic agent is given an initial endowment at the outset, and after a sequence of market transactions, consumes the commodities in their possession at the

final point in time. Here, each agent optimizes their strategy, which can be expressed by supply and demand functions. When prices in all markets are consistent with the intersection of supply and demand curves, all agents are satisfied with the outcomes, resulting in an equilibrium state of the markets. Although his focus on equilibrium in supply and demand functions differs in appearance from Jevons's utility-maximization approach, Walras emphasized that there are no essential differences between their claims and that the two approaches are complementary.

When comparing the Walrasian model with Jevons's model, both approaches share a common feature of static modeling, whereas Walras extends it from a single-market model to a multiple-markets model. In other words, the temporal continuity of market exchanges is likewise abstracted away in the Walrasian model. After the final point in time, no further exchanges are permitted, and the commodities held by agents can only be consumed by themselves. That is, all exchanges must be completed by the final point in time.

2.3 Arrow–Debreu's General Equilibrium Model

Over half a century after Walras's proposal, the general equilibrium model evolved from the Walrasian model to the Arrow–Debreu model (Debreu 1959). This model incorporates dynamic extensions by assuming a finite time axis which is divided into a finite number of intervals (Debreu 1959, p. 29). At the end of each interval, goods cannot be carried over to the next interval and must be entirely consumed by their owner, as is the case in earlier models.¹ As it stands, this modeling has no difference from simply arranging multiple Walrasian models along a time axis. However, by assuming the hypothetical futures markets, interactions across different intervals are introduced, and thus the Arrow–Debreu model effectively equips the Walrasian model with dynamic features.

However, the assumption underlying the Arrow–Debreu model—that once the end of the time interval is reached, all goods become no longer exchangeable and must be consumed by their owner—raises questions about its validity, as it clearly deviates from reality.² In actual markets, opportunities for exchange continue to exist at any given point in time, and there is no moment at which all exchanges are completed simultaneously. This characteristic is a specific feature in exchange over time, which is absent in static models. Therefore, it is difficult to assert that the Arrow–Debreu model fully addresses Jevons's concerns regarding dynamic aspects, despite its apparent dynamic extension.

¹In (Debreu 1959, p. 54), the condition is stated as follows: *"The preferences considered here take no account of the resale value of commodities; the i th consumer is interested in these only for the sake of the personal use he is going to make of them."*

²Mainstream economists often respond to the critique of unreality of assumptions by citing Friedman's instrumentalism (Friedman 1953), arguing that the validity of a theory should be judged not by the realism of its assumptions, but by the accuracy of its prediction. However, as will be shown in the following sections, the static modeling that divides the time dimension exerts a substantial influence on the outcomes of exchange theory. In fact, both marginal utility theory and market equilibrium theory are supported by few empirical evidences. Consequently, the above assumption may not be justifiable even from an instrumentalist view.

2.4 Discussion

A key limitation of mainstream economics, which is based on UTV characterized by its static nature, is the difficulty of appropriately integrating the role of money into its exchange theory. The reason is that, at the end of each interval, the exchangeability of all goods is lost, and therefore there is no benefit in holding money until the end, as money itself possesses no intrinsic utility. As a result, rational agents would refuse to accept money at the terminal point and attempt to exchange all their holdings of money slightly before the terminal point. Anticipating that others would adopt the same strategy, however, no one would be willing to accept money even a moment earlier. By applying this logic recursively, it follows that from the very beginning no agents would accept money in exchange, making it difficult to justify the existence of money.

Several proposals have been made to incorporate money into the general equilibrium model, for examples, by introducing “frictions” in transactions conducted without money (Hicks 1989 [1935]), or by imposing certain constraints on monetary balances at the end of each interval (Patinkin 1971 [1965]), thereby seeking to justify the existence of money. Nevertheless, none of these approaches can be said to have yielded satisfactory results (Benetti 2004). Due to the difficulty of incorporating money into the general equilibrium model, many macroeconomic models assume a barter economy where money does not virtually exist. However, the assertion—commonly referred to as the “veil of money” view—that a monetary economy can be approximated by a barter economy lacks sufficient theoretical argument and is contrary to common intuition.

In conclusion, mainstream exchange theory has consistently applied a static approach, adopting a closed time axis with single or multiple intervals of finite length. This approach allows mathematical treatment of human behavior through the utility maximization problem. However, this comes at the cost of assuming the existence of moments at which all exchanges are completed simultaneously. Due to this unrealistic assumption, mainstream theories of value and exchange struggle to handle money properly, compelling them to often exclude it from analysis. Taken together, these considerations make it clear that UTV with static characteristic is fundamentally incompatible with MMT, which places money at the core of its theory.

3 Value Theory in Dynamics

In the previous section, we highlighted that the exchange theory of mainstream economics is based on static models. Due to the constraints arising from this assumption, UTV is fundamentally incompatible with MMT. Accordingly, developing a theory of value consistent with MMT requires a theoretical framework that accurately reflects the temporal continuity of exchanges. In this section, we remove the assumption inherent in static models that “all exchanges are completed simultaneously at certain moments” and investigate a dynamic theory of value (DTV) grounded in continuous exchange.

Apart from its dynamic extensions, the framework of DTV is informed by mainstream economics. Its behavioral assumptions relax the constraints of rationality to achieve a

more realistic representation than that of neoclassical theory. Nevertheless, due to mathematical requirements, a certain degree of rationality remains. As a result, compared to other heterodox schools, our framework shares numerous commonalities with neoclassical mathematical economics, particularly in terminology and notations. Yet, these issues have been redefined here to clarify our argument.

3.1 The Polysemous Nature of Utility

As noted earlier, Jevons described that the notion of utility stems from pleasure and pain experienced by human beings.³ However, the magnitude of such pleasure is inherently subjective and cannot be measured directly. He therefore argued that the magnitude of pleasure can be estimated externally from the choices regarding which goods to prefer.

Let us recall that Jevons’s definition of utility, which is grounded in pleasure, implicitly ignores the potential for future exchanges of possessions. Within this framework, a strategy that maximizes total pleasure is simply to pursue exchanging one’s current holdings for goods expected to yield greater pleasure. Thus, the utility function—as a measure of pleasure—can also serve as decision criteria for the individual. Moreover, in the absence of a temporal dimension, it scarcely matters whether the object of judgment is the act of choosing goods or the goods themselves. Consequently, within Jevons’s framework of UTV, the notion of utility treats the following questions as essentially equivalent:

- Which one yields greater pleasure?
- Which activity should be chosen?
- Which goods should be chosen?

As Jevons explicitly noted, the assumption that the exchangeability of possessions is eliminated at the final point in time was imposed due to the technical limitations of his era. In transitioning from a static to a dynamic model, this assumption must be removed. In a dynamic setting, a strategy that maximizes the total utility of possessions at the end of each period may no longer be optimal for individuals, since it dismisses the possibility of further utility gains from subsequent exchanges. In other words, it is inappropriate to equate a utility function—which serves as a measurement of pleasure—with the criteria for choosing goods. Furthermore, the introduction of temporality necessitates a distinction between two subtly different questions: whether the object of judgment is the act of choosing goods, or the goods themselves.

Consequently, adhering to the traditional usage of the term “utility,” which has three distinct meanings in a dynamic setting, will inevitably lead to confusion in the subsequent discussion. Given this into account, we introduce new terminology for the three aforementioned concepts, thereby distinguishing them from the traditional meaning of “utility.”

³In what follows, the term “pleasure and pain” is abbreviated to “pleasure.”

3.2 Preference over Activities

Here, in the context of DTV, we define the term corresponding to the question "Which activity should be chosen?" and refer to it as "Preference over Activities" (PoA).

Definition 3.1 (Preference over Activities). *Preference over Activities (PoA)* is an ordering relation that prioritizes *sequences of actions* available to an agent in a given *situation*, indicating which sequence is more desirable. Here, 'available' implies *sequences of actions* restricted not only by budgetary and capability constraints, but also by habits and conventions.

It is worthwhile to stress the difference between PoA and the conventional usage of the term "preference." Traditionally, preference is treated as a ranking over goods—a static notion. In contrast, PoA specifies a ranking over activities—a dynamic notion, which focuses on the act of choosing rather than the goods themselves. This subtle difference results in an essential divergence in assumptions regarding the rationality of economic agents. This is because the traditional notion of preference, when defined over goods, inevitably envisages economic agents who maximize the total utility of their final holdings—as suggested by the general equilibrium model—thereby imposing the assumptions of perfect rationality, such as full access to information, advanced computational abilities, and perfect foresight. On the other hand, when preference is defined over a sequence of actions, it merely assumes that the agent follows a biological decision-making mechanism, without requiring the aforementioned assumptions of perfect rationality. Furthermore, by incorporating additional conditions of habits and conventions, the definition avoids assumption of perfect rationality, in which agents are able to identify the optimal option among a vast number of alternatives. As such, our definition of PoA is more compatible with bounded rationality.

We now further clarify the definition of PoA. While the terms "situation" and "sequence of actions" are used in the definition, they are not common terminology in economics. Within the framework of DTV, the term "situation" is defined as follows:

Definition 3.2 (Situation). A *situation* is all information relevant to the evaluation of activities faced by a particular individual.

This includes the current holdings, capabilities, desires, location, the observable external environment, and accessible economic information. Although some of these elements are attributed to the individual, the individual *per se* is excluded from the definition. Instead, it emerges through differences of PoA under the same situation.

Additionally, regarding the "sequence of actions," unresolved issues remain concerning the temporal scope of decision-making. This issue is also related to a fundamental question in economics concerning the level of cognitive capacity of economic agents. Core theories in mainstream economics assume perfect rationality in individuals, which is resulted from the technical requirement that the difficulty of handling uncertainty in algebraic modeling

approach, despite acknowledging its deviation from reality. Nonetheless, within DTV framework, the temporal scope of decision-making is asserted limited period for the following reasons:

- Since the objective of this study is to develop a theory of value consistent with MMT, it is more preferable to adopt bounded rationality rather than perfect rationality.
- Even if economic agents select mathematically optimal strategies, deterministic conclusions are not necessarily guaranteed. In game theory, it is well known fact that optimal strategies are not uniquely determined in general, making it essentially impossible to predict which option will be selected. As will be shown in the next section, the exchange theory derived from DTV also produces outcomes involving uncertainty.
- Most importantly, uncertainty can be properly formulated mathematically once we abandon the ultimate goal of a complete description of the entire system and instead treat it as an open system. Given the foundational premise of this study—an economy in which exchanges continue—we consequently need to analyze the system without terminal point on the time axis. A perfect rational approach to such a system typically requires strong assumptions, such as modeling by overlapping generations, thereby undermining the practical relevance of the resulting analysis. However, such technical difficulties can be alleviated by describing the economy as an open system.

Considering above, we define “sequence of actions” or ”activity” for short, as follows:

Definition 3.3 (Sequence of Actions). *Sequence of actions* or *activity* is a time series of actions within the temporal scope that an agent is capable of planning, beginning with an initial state and ending with a terminal state.

For clarity, the structure of activity is illustrated in Figure 3. In this context, the state includes only attributes and conditions specific to the individual—such as their possessions and desires—and excludes any external environment factors.

Figure 3: Sequence of actions

We have defined the basis of decision-making as ”situation,” including the agent’s current state along with the prevailing external environment. Given bounded rationality, an agent

should be able predict the subsequent state after the sequence of actions is conducted.⁴ For instance, an agent can readily foresee that, when they spend their budget or consume food stored in the refrigerator, their holdings will decrease by the same amount. Accordingly, the information that an agent can access with sufficient accuracy consists of: (i) partial information on the current environment, (ii) agent's current state, (iii) available activities, and (iv) the agent's resulting state after executing the selected activity.⁵ All other elements are uncertain and unknown to the agent. Beyond the scope of planning, the agent cannot forecast even their own future state. Nor can the agent predict the behavior of other agents or changes in the external environment. Hence, these uncertain factors are beyond the scope of their decision-making.

In what follows, PoA of a particular individual under a certain situation \mathcal{S} will be described by $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$.^{6 7} For instance, $x \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} y$ denotes that activity y is indifferent to or preferable to activity x under situation \mathcal{S} . Obeying the conventional description, other ordering symbols ($\succeq_{\mathcal{S}}$, $\prec_{\mathcal{S}}$, $\succ_{\mathcal{S}}$, $\sim_{\mathcal{S}}$) are defined as follows:

- $x \succeq_{\mathcal{S}} y \Leftrightarrow y \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} x$
- $x \prec_{\mathcal{S}} y \Leftrightarrow (x \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} y) \wedge (y \not\preceq_{\mathcal{S}} x)$
- $x \succ_{\mathcal{S}} y \Leftrightarrow y \prec_{\mathcal{S}} x$
- $x \sim_{\mathcal{S}} y \Leftrightarrow (x \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} y) \wedge (x \succeq_{\mathcal{S}} y)$

Here, the diagonal slash on $\not\preceq$ denotes negation. $x \sim_{\mathcal{S}} y$ indicates that both activities x and y are indifferent under situation \mathcal{S} .

For ease of mathematical treatment, we introduce the following assumption regarding PoA:

Assumption 3.4 (Rationality of Preference). Under any situation, including hypothetical one, PoA satisfies complete preordering. That is, given any available activities x, y, z , the PoA $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$ satisfies the following conditions:

- Reflexivity : $x \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} x$
- Completeness: $(x \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} y) \vee (y \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} x)$
- Transitivity : $(x \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} y) \wedge (y \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} z) \Rightarrow x \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} z$

⁴Although, unforeseen events may prevent the execution of a plan, or an agent may change their mind in the middle of the way, decision-making is usually conducted under the presumption that the planned activity will be executed without failure.

⁵For simplicity, this paper does not consider the probabilistic branching of activities.

⁶To specify the individual of concern, a notation such as $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}^i$ may be introduced, thereby indicating the preference relation of individual i . Nonetheless, we shall henceforth denote it simply as $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$ for the sake of simplicity.

⁷Hereafter, we mainly use the term "PoA" under a specific situation, as indicated by $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$. However, we occasionally use it to refer to an individual's decision-making principle without restricting it to a particular situation.

where "hypothetical one" indicates an unrealistic situation that is either unlikely or impossible to occur. As will be shown in Section 3.3 and Section 4.1, allowing PoA to be defined under such situations is useful for introducing derivative concepts of PoA.

It is essential to examine the validity of Assumption 3.4. The assumption of rational consistency is also adopted in neoclassical economics (Samuelson 1938). However, the assertion of rational human behavior has long been subject to critique. In particular, the transitivity condition is a notably strong assumption, implying that a consistent ordering can be assigned across the entire set of activities. For instance, when faced with 100 alternatives, it is assumed that the economic agent can provide a consistent preference ordering for all $100 \times 99/2$ possible pairs. As demonstrated by (Sippel 1997), such an assumption is often violated by empirical results. Despite these concerns, we proceed with our discussion under Assumption 3.4 for the following reasons. First, the set of choices considered by the PoA is restricted to habitual behaviors, which likely mitigates the difficulty of satisfying consistency compared with conventional economic theory. Second, the subsequent analysis presented in this paper does not heavily rely on the transitivity condition and is expected to be robust to some deviations. Third, our primary objective is to emphasize the importance of considering continuous exchanges, rather than to criticize the notion of the *homo economicus*. In summary, while it cannot be denied that the present analysis may be affected to some extent by the divergence between assumption and reality, this issue is not expected to affect the essential outcomes of our study.

3.3 Expected Utility for Comparing Goods

We now turn to a concept associated with the choice of goods. It has already been noted that the traditional notion of utility cannot be treated as criteria for choosing goods within DTV framework. Since goods remain exchangeable at any moment in time, the criteria for choosing goods must consider not only the utility of the goods at hand but also the potential utility of goods that will be obtained through future exchanges. To capture this idea, we introduce a new term "expected utility (EU)" in this subsection, following several preparatory definitions and notations.

Definition 3.5 (Bundle of Goods). *A bundle of goods, or simply goods, is a collection of transferable resources or assets within an economic system, including both tangible and intangible items, as well as their combinations.*

When there are N types of goods in the economy, the bundle can be represented as an N -dimensional real vector. Negative values are permitted, which indicate a loss of the corresponding item. The zero vector $\mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ represents void goods. Arithmetic operations such as addition and subtraction between goods (+, -), as well as multiplication and division by scalar values (\cdot , /), are naturally defined through vector arithmetic. For instance, for any $A, B \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $A + B$ denotes goods whose components are the sum of the corresponding components of the vectors representing goods A and B , whereas $-A$ or $(-1) \cdot A$ indicates goods in which acquisition and loss are reversed for each component

of A . Vectors of goods can be compared as follows: for any $A, B \in \mathbb{R}^N$, we write $A < B$ if and only if $A_i \leq B_i$ holds for all components $i = 1 \cdots N$, and there exists at least one component j such that $A_j < B_j$. All of these definitions adhere to the framework of mainstream microeconomics. The only difference lies in the explicit inclusion of financial instruments, such as money, as goods.

For convenience, we introduce a notation that allows the construction of a hypothetical situation derived from a partial modification of the possession of goods under a certain situation. Specifically, given a situation \mathcal{S} , we denote by \mathcal{S}_A the new situation in which the individual's possession of goods is 'added' by goods A , *ceteris paribus*. Negative components of $A \in \mathbb{R}^N$ represent reductions in the corresponding items. The PoA associated with the new situation \mathcal{S}_A is denoted by $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}_A}$.

We then define "Preference over Goods" (PoG) as a case-specific variant of PoA.

Definition 3.6 (Preference over Goods). The *Preference over Goods (PoG)*, at a given situation, represents the preference ordering over a set of goods according to the associated PoA, under a hypothetical offer whereby the individual can obtain one of them for free.

As a logical convenience, non-receivable goods must be inferior to any receivable goods, while no ordering is defined between two non-receivable goods.

Suppose that an individual is offered either two apples or one banana at no cost. If the act of acquiring two apples is indifferent to the act of acquiring one banana in terms of the individual's PoA, the two goods are equivalent in terms of the corresponding PoG. In addition, if the individual prefers two apples to one banana, the former is superior to the latter in terms of the PoG. The offer is made at a particular situation, which is an external intervention to a specific individual in the system, without affecting the holdings of other individuals. Since such a scenario would not occur in practice, the notion of PoG is based on a hypothetical premise.

The ordering relation of PoG can be represented by using the aforementioned notations. For instance, given $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$ as the corresponding PoA under the same situation, $A \prec_{\mathcal{S}} B$ represents that the goods A is inferior to goods B under situation \mathcal{S} , while $A \sim_{\mathcal{S}} B$ indicates that two goods are equivalent under situation \mathcal{S} .⁸

It is important to note that the set of goods available to 'receive' is restricted by the current possession state. This is because if the bundle of goods contains negative vector components, the operations may involve payments or losses beyond the available budget. Accordingly, the PoG does not define a complete preorder over the entire goods space \mathbb{R}^N ,

⁸Strictly speaking, these notations are not rigorous because $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$ are defined to operate activities rather than goods. Accordingly, another ordering $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}'}$ should be defined so as to represent PoG by $A \prec_{\mathcal{S}'} B$. Nevertheless, no practical inconsistency arises from this simplified notation, since each PoA has a unique corresponding PoG. Hence, we apply this notation hereafter for simplicity's sake.

but instead satisfies only a partial preorder.⁹ For the same reason, \mathcal{S}_A may not exist for a given pair of (\mathcal{S}, A) . To ensure the completeness of ordering relation $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$ as PoG, the domain must be restricted from the entire goods space \mathbb{R}^N to the set of receivable goods, formally expressed as $\{X \in \mathbb{R}^N \mid \exists \mathcal{S}_X\}$.^{10 11}

We are now ready to define the *expected utility* as follows:

Definition 3.7 (Expected Utility). An *expected utility function* is a function that represents the ordering relation of a given PoG. Formally, it is defined as a function $EU(\cdot; \preceq_{\mathcal{S}}) : \{X \in \mathbb{R}^N \mid \exists \mathcal{S}_X\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that maps the receivable goods space to the real numbers and satisfies the following condition:

$$\forall A, B \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad EU(A; \preceq_{\mathcal{S}}) \leq EU(B; \preceq_{\mathcal{S}}) \Leftrightarrow A \preceq_{\mathcal{S}} B$$

Additionally, the output value of the function is called *expected utility*.¹²

Here, the semicolon separating the arguments indicates that the subsequent $\preceq_{\mathcal{S}}$ is a parameter of the function rather than a variable. When it is clear from the context, we simply write $EU(\cdot)$.

The previous example, stating that “two apples are superior to one banana in terms of the PoG,” can be restated as “the EU of two apples is greater than that of one banana.” As such, EU can be expressed as if it were an attribute of goods, providing a more intuitive representation. For the remainder of this paper, we mainly use the term “EU” instead of “PoG.”

The two notions—the utility in UTV and EU in DTV—share the common feature of measuring the desirability of goods. In addition, as with the utility function, the EU function is not uniquely determined, and its value lacks physical interpretation. The key difference is that, unlike the former, the latter does not presuppose the agent to consume the goods by themselves, thereby preserving exchangeability of goods across periods. As a specific example, consider the case of choosing between two commodities at a shop. Within UTV, it is assumed that an individual chooses a commodity by comparing the pleasure derived from it with the pain associated with its cost. Within DTV, however, it

⁹A partial preorder is an ordering relation that is identical to a complete preorder, except that completeness is not guaranteed.

¹⁰This notation implicitly assumes that goods A can be received whenever the situation \mathcal{S}_X exists. Nowadays, most countries guarantee basic property rights, so this assumption is deemed plausible.

¹¹Various types of commodities are indivisible and can only be obtained in integer quantities. This point could be incorporated into the existence conditions of \mathcal{S}_X , which would allow for a more realistic analysis.

¹²Notice that our use of the term “expected utility” differs from the standard terminology. Typically, it refers to the expected value of utility over future events with known probabilities. In contrast, our use of “expected” refers not to probabilistic expectations, but to the consideration of future exchangeability. Nonetheless, assuming perfectly rational agent who maximizes the expectation of utility gains, the two definitions will become essentially equivalent. Therefore, our definition of EU can be regarded as a generalization of the conventional one, and is unlikely to cause significant confusion.

assumes that an individual makes decisions while also considering future actions, such as whether a chosen commodity can be exchanged with another person, or what can be purchased with the remaining budget.

While the above definition follows utility function in mathematical economics, the more relaxed definition facilitates the subsequent arguments, as will be shown in Definition 3.14.

Definition 3.8 (Expected Utility with Infinity). A *quasi-expected utility function* provides a limited representation of the ordering relation of a given PoG. Formally, it is defined as a function $EU(\cdot; \succsim_S) : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ that maps the goods space to the extended real numbers and satisfies the following conditions for any goods $A, B \in \mathbb{R}^N$:

$$\begin{aligned} -\infty < EU(A; \succsim_S) = EU(B; \succsim_S) < +\infty &\Rightarrow A \sim_S B \\ EU(A; \succsim_S) < EU(B; \succsim_S) &\Leftrightarrow A \prec_S B \\ EU(A; \succsim_S) = -\infty &\Leftrightarrow A \notin \{X \in \mathbb{R}^N \mid \exists S_X\} \end{aligned}$$

For clarity, the set of extended real numbers is a set of real numbers augmented with two elements, $-\infty$ and $+\infty$, defined as $\overline{\mathbb{R}} := \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty, +\infty\}$, which obey the following ordering relation:

$$-\infty < x < +\infty \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}$$

Like a normal expected utility function, the output of the function defined above is also called *expected utility*.

A key difference from the original (Definition 3.7) is that the comparison between $+\infty$ and $-\infty$ does not yield the corresponding preference ordering.¹³ In this sense, a quasi-expected utility function is only a limited representation of PoG. Furthermore, the domain of the function is extended to the entire goods space \mathbb{R}^N by assigning $-\infty$ to all non-receivable goods.

Here, we impose a few assumptions concerning the rationality of economic agents. We first assume that obtaining positive amount of goods for free is always beneficial regardless of their quality.

Assumption 3.9 (Positive Preferences over Goods). Under any PoA, the EU of any goods with a positive quantity is greater than void goods. That is:

$$\forall \succsim_S, \forall A \in \mathbb{R}^N, \mathbf{0} < A \Rightarrow \mathbf{0} \prec_S A$$

In addition, we introduce another assumption concerning the consistency of preferences over post-possession states (Assumption 3.10).

¹³In contrast, the comparison between $-\infty$ and $-\infty$ indicates that both goods are non-receivable, and thus associated preference ordering is undefined (See Definition 3.6).

Assumption 3.10 (Ex-Post Consistency of Preferences). Given a pair of PoA $(\succsim_S, \succsim_{S_A})$, the following equivalence holds:

$$\forall B, C \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad B \succsim_{S_A} C \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad A + B \succsim_S A + C$$

In other words, if goods C is weakly preferred to goods B in a situation where the agent already possesses goods A , then goods $(A + C)$ must also be weakly preferred to goods $(A + B)$ when goods A is not yet possessed. Otherwise, the agent's evaluations would be inconsistent across two situations that are ex-post identical. Corresponding relationships can be derived for the other ordering relations based on the above assumption.

Proposition 3.11 (Ex-Post Consistency of Preferences). Assumption 3.10 also holds for other ordering relations $(\sim_S, \prec_S, \succ_S, \succeq_S)$. In other words, given a pair of PoA $(\succsim_S, \succsim_{S_A})$, the following equivalences hold for any goods $B, C \in \mathbb{R}^N$:

$$\begin{aligned} B \sim_{S_A} C &\Leftrightarrow A + B \sim_S A + C \\ B \prec_{S_A} C &\Leftrightarrow A + B \prec_S A + C \\ B \succ_{S_A} C &\Leftrightarrow A + B \succ_S A + C \\ B \succeq_{S_A} C &\Leftrightarrow A + B \succeq_S A + C \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Due to the basic property of ordering: $x \succeq y \Leftrightarrow y \preceq x$, it is evident that the case of \succeq_S follows from Assumption 3.10. For the same reason, if either case of \prec_{S_A} or \succ_{S_A} holds, so does the other. Accordingly, it is sufficient to prove only two cases: \sim_{S_A} and \prec_{S_A} .

Case of \sim_{S_A} :

$$\begin{aligned} & B \sim_{S_A} C \\ \Leftrightarrow & B \succsim_{S_A} C \quad \wedge \quad B \succeq_{S_A} C \\ \Leftrightarrow & A + B \succsim_S A + C \quad \wedge \quad A + B \succeq_S A + C \\ \Leftrightarrow & A + B \sim_S A + C \end{aligned}$$

Case of \prec_{S_A} :

$$\begin{aligned} & B \prec_{S_A} C \\ \Leftrightarrow & B \not\succeq_{S_A} C \\ \Leftrightarrow & A + B \not\succeq_S A + C \\ \Leftrightarrow & A + B \prec_S A + C \end{aligned}$$

□

In summary, the choice between goods B and C in a situation where goods A is already possessed must be consistent with the choice between goods $(A + B)$ and goods $(A + C)$ in a situation where goods A is not yet possessed.

A key distinction from UTV is that our framework explicitly asserts the existence of an inherent asymmetry between obtaining and losing goods. In other words, the following statements are not equivalent:

- Obtaining goods A is indifference to obtaining goods B .
- Paying with goods A to obtain goods B is indifferent to doing nothing.
- Paying with goods B to obtain goods A is indifferent to doing nothing.
- Losing goods A is indifferent to losing goods B .

These statements are equivalent in terms of relative changes in possessions; however, the absolute level of possessions differs after the choices. To ensure the equivalences of statements above, it is necessary to consider the differences in possession states as follows:

Corollary 3.12. Given a pair of PoA $(\succ_S, \succ_{S_A}, \succ_{S_B}, \succ_{S_{A+B}})$, the following equivalences hold:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & A \sim_S B \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \mathbf{0} \sim_{S_A} B - A \\
 \Leftrightarrow & A - B \sim_{S_B} \mathbf{0} \\
 \Leftrightarrow & -B \sim_{S_{A+B}} -A
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, all the statements above hold when the symbols \sim are replaced by $\prec, \succ, \succeq,$ or \succeq .

Proof. The result follows immediately from Assumption 3.10 and Proposition 3.11. The proof is straightforward. \square

In light of these considerations, it is inappropriate to regard EU as an intrinsic property of goods, unlike mass or size attributed to physical objects. Rather, EU is a conceptual projection of PoA onto the object, and is therefore subject to external environment. This point will be revisited in later discussion.

The above assumptions and propositions naturally lead to the monotonicity property of EU, which is commonly known as *non-satiation*.

Proposition 3.13 (Non-Satiation). The EU of goods is greater than lower quantity of goods. That is:

$$\forall(\succ_S, \succ_{S_A}), \forall A, B \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad A < B \Rightarrow A \prec_S B$$

Proof. Since $A < B$, we have $\mathbf{0} < B - A$. By Assumption 3.9, and noting that PoA can be chosen arbitrarily, it follows that $\mathbf{0} \prec_{S_A} B - A$. Hence, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{0} \prec_{S_A} B - A \\ \Leftrightarrow & A + \mathbf{0} \prec_S A + (B - A) \\ \Leftrightarrow & A \prec_S B \end{aligned}$$

□

As such, EU is monotonic. Accordingly, for any given EU of a certain goods, there exists at most one quantity of a particular goods $A > \mathbf{0}$ that yields the same EU. We now consider restricting the EU function—which is not uniquely defined—so as to obtain a desirable form, by exploiting its monotonicity.

Definition 3.14 (Scaled Expected Utility). Let \prec_S be a PoA, and let $A \in \{a \in \mathbb{R}^N \mid a > \mathbf{0}\}$ denote a non-zero, non-negative goods. The *expected utility (EU) function with goods A as the numeraire*, $EU(\cdot; \prec_S, A) : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$, is a quasi-expected utility function that satisfies the following condition:

$$\forall s \in \{s \in \mathbb{R} \mid \exists S_{s,A}\}, \quad EU(s \cdot A; \prec_S, A) = s$$

When there is no risk of confusion, we simply write $EU_A(\cdot)$ instead of $EU(\cdot; \prec_S, A)$.

This function exhibits the following desirable properties:

Proposition 3.15 (Numeraire as a Measurement). The expected utility function EU_A , with goods A as the *numeraire*, has the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned} EU_A(X) = s & \Leftrightarrow s \cdot A \sim_S X, & (s \in \{t \in \mathbb{R} \mid \exists S_{t,A}\}) \\ EU_A(X) = +\infty & \Leftrightarrow s \cdot A \prec_S X, & (\forall s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Straightforward. It suffices to apply Definition 3.14 and 3.8, as well as basic properties of ordering.

1st(= s) \Rightarrow :

By Definition 3.14, we have

$$EU_A(X) = EU_A(s \cdot A) = s$$

Since s is a real number, it follows that

$$-\infty < EU_A(X) = EU_A(s \cdot A) < +\infty$$

Hence, applying the first condition of Definition 3.8 yields $s \cdot A \sim_S X$.

1st(= s) \Leftarrow :

For the completeness of the ordering \succsim_s among receivable goods,

$$s \cdot A \sim_s X \Leftrightarrow (s \cdot A \not\prec_s X) \wedge (s \cdot A \not\succeq_s X)$$

must hold. By Definition 3.8, this is equivalent to

$$(EU_A(s \cdot A) \not\prec EU_A(X)) \wedge (EU_A(s \cdot A) \not\succeq EU_A(X))$$

Since the extended real numbers $\overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is also complete as an order, it follows that $EU_A(X) = EU_A(s \cdot A) = s$.

2nd(+ ∞) \Rightarrow :

Since $s < +\infty$ for any $s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, $EU_A(s \cdot A) < EU_A(X)$ must hold. Thus, $s \cdot A \prec_s X$ is immediately obtained by the second condition of Definition 3.8.

2nd(+ ∞) \Leftarrow :

Applying the second condition of Definition 3.8, along with Definition 3.14 yields

$$\begin{aligned} & s \cdot A \prec_s X && (\forall s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}) \\ \Leftrightarrow & EU_A(s \cdot A) < EU_A(X) && (\forall s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}) \\ \Leftrightarrow & s < EU_A(X) && (\forall s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}) \end{aligned}$$

$EU_A(X) \in \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ must be $+\infty$; otherwise, $s < EU_A(X)$ cannot be satisfied for any $s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$.

□

In other words, EU function with goods A as the *numeraire* is a function that maps any given goods $X \in \mathbb{R}^N$ to the quantity of *numeraire* A that makes the recipient indifferent between the two, thereby allowing preferences over goods of various kinds and quantities to be compared on a single scale.¹⁴ The EU function returns $+\infty$ if the given goods cannot be balanced by any finite quantity of *numeraire*. This may occur, for example, when the agent holds a sufficient amount of the *numeraire*, or when the goods in question are indispensable. As previously noted, the EU function does not determine the relative preference between goods whose EU is $+\infty$. Therefore, a preferable *numeraire* is one that minimizes such indeterminate cases, and money is well suited for this role due to the limitless demands for it.

One feature of the scaled EU function is that the absolute magnitude of the *numeraire* carries no intrinsic meaning. For instance, if goods A is assigned an EU value of 10 when the function is scaled by one liter of water, then it must be assigned a value of 5 when the function is scaled by two liters of water, since the total quantities are identical. Hence, the statement "the EU of the goods X equals to 10 liters of water" is an unambiguous expression. In what follows, we use this notation.

¹⁴The quasi-linear utility function in mathematical economics plays an similar role (Varian 2007 [2005]). In this sense, the EU function with *numeraire* can be regarded as a dynamic extension of the quasi-linear utility function.

3.4 Pleasure as Physiological Stimulus

Jevons argued that one could infer the degree of pleasure from the externally observable results of human actions. This Benthamite utilitarian approach, which sought to explain behavior in terms of pleasure, was gradually abandoned in later economics. Pareto redefined the notion of utility as an ordinal scale that consistently represents preferences of choices, thereby separating it from psychological pleasure—widely recognized as the pivotal move from cardinal to ordinal utility (Pareto 2014 [1906/1909]). This shift reflects an underlying intention to construct a market theory independent of the measurability of utility, given the technical difficulty of quantifying the degree of pleasure (Moscati 2018, pp. 80–82).

Following Pareto’s approach, our framework distinguishes the notion of individual decision criteria (i.e., PoA) from the psychological factor. Yet, it cannot be denied that emotional elements—such as seeking pleasure and avoiding pain—substantially influence human decision-making, as revealed by recent neuroscience studies (Camerer, Loewenstein, and Prelec 2005). On this basis, our framework regards pleasure as one of the input factors in the formation of PoA as a biological process.

Thus, the new terminology allows us to resolve the ambiguity concerning the notion of utility, as noted in Section 3.1. The question “Which one yields greater pleasure?” concerns to the notion of pleasure. The question “Which activity should be chosen?” is addressed by PoA, whereas “Which goods should be chosen?” is judged by EU (or PoG). By clarifying the terminology in this manner, the long-standing controversy over cardinal and ordinal utility in UTV is naturally resolved. Assuming that pleasure corresponds to a certain physiological signal pulse, it may be considered cardinal. PoA is clearly ordinal by definition. While EU is generally ordinal, it becomes cardinal when scaled by a *numeraire*. Therefore, the confusion between cardinal and ordinal utility arises from the multiplicity of meanings for the term “utility.”

3.5 Value as Exchange Ratio

Traditionally, economics defines the value of goods as its exchange value, which is reflected in the exchange ratio with others (Mill 1909, p. 314; Jevons 1888, p. 70). In the present paper, we also adopt this conventional definition. For example, if goods *A* and goods *B* are traded at a ratio of 1:2 in the market, one may say that “goods *A* is worth twice as much as goods *B*.” If goods *A* and *B* cannot be exchanged directly, the value is expressed in terms of their indirect exchange ratio through other goods.

The notion of value as a market exchange ratio is often confused with the degree of desirability that an individual assigns to goods (i.e., EU) but the two notions are strictly distinct. Suppose an individual is offered goods *A* and *B* and is free to choose one; if the individual selects goods *A*, it is commonly said that “goods *A* is more valuable than goods *B*.” However, in our definitions, such a statement refers to EU, not to value as a means of exchange ratio. EU serves as criteria at the individual level, whereas value arises from social agreement. The necessity of this strict distinction will become evident in later

discussions.

3.6 Prevailing Misconceptions in Value Theory

EU and value, defined in the context of human behavior, are abstract concepts inseparable from their dynamic aspect. However, human awareness and concern are usually directed toward visible objects, making it extremely difficult for most people to perceive the invisible influence of future exchangeability on these concepts. As a result, most people commit the error of reflecting EU and value—originally dynamic concepts—onto goods as if they were static concepts intrinsic to object. This fallacy is evident in common phrases such as “this product has greater value” or “this commodity is worth X yen,” where EU and value are treated as intrinsic properties of goods.¹⁵

However, there is yet another fallacy concerning value. A more significant, but consistently overlooked point is that EU (or PoG) and value (or prices) interact with each other. The influence of the former on the latter—how the aggregate of individuals’ preference for commodities affects market prices—is relatively comprehensible. For instance, a person would not be willing to pay a higher price for a commodity unless they desire it more strongly than the other. By observing the marketplace, it becomes apparent that a commodity with superior functionality is generally sold at a higher price. However, it is rarely acknowledged that market prices also influence individual’s PoG.

Suppose you are currently thirsty and, although somewhat unrealistic, a friend to whom you are indebted appears and offers you a choice between bottled water and some amount of money for free. A bottle of the same water can be purchased at a nearby store for 100 yen. A question is, how much money is needed to justify receiving cash instead of the water? The answer to this problem is simple. Regardless of how thirsty you are, it is rational to receive the cash exactly when the offered amount exceeds 100 yen. This is because, after receiving the cash, you can immediately purchase the same bottle of water at the nearby store and gain some profit. Conversely, if the offered amount is less than 100 yen, it is better to select the water for free. The two options break even when the amount offered is precisely 100 yen. Therefore, in this situation, the EU of bottled water and the EU of money equivalent to its market price are in terms of your PoG. A remarkable point is that the EU of bottled water, denominated in money of account, is not directly related to the properties of the commodity, such as scarcity or marginal utility. In other words, it is not that your strength of desire (i.e., EU) influences the market price; rather, the market price influences how strongly you desire the commodity.

Let us consider another example. Once again, you are thirsty, and a friend to whom you are indebted offers you either bottled water or a premium beer for free. If you enjoy alcohol, it would be rational to choose the beer without hesitation. However, suppose you cannot drink alcohol at all. Under the constraint that you consume it by yourself, it is more rational for you to choose the bottled water, which provides greater utility. Nevertheless, when

¹⁵It has been similarly emphasized by Jevons that utility and value are not intrinsic to goods (Jevons 1888, pp. 49, 69).

future exchangeability is taken into account, choosing the beer also becomes an option. That is, if you sell the beer and use the obtained money to acquire water, you can make profits by the margin.

The implication of these two cases is that UTV cannot be sustained when future exchanges are taken into account. In a dynamic setting, PoG depends not only on their intrinsic properties, such as functionality or scarcity, but also on market prices. This is the opposite of the common belief that the desirability of a commodity is reflected in its market price. Let us now analyze the mechanism behind why such a reversal occurs.

As is evident from its notion \preceq_s , PoA is dependent on situation. Hence, pleasure and market prices, involved in situation, must influence PoA. Moreover, EU function takes PoA as a parameter (See Definition 3.8). It is not yet clear how market prices are determined when temporal continuity of exchange is taken into account. Nevertheless, given that activities of market participants consist of sequences of commodities choices, market prices must be a function that takes EU functions of all participants as its arguments. Considering these, the causal structure among these concepts can be illustrated in terms of function – argument relationship, as shown in Figure 4.¹⁶ It shows that EU and value mutually interact directly or indirectly. The causal relationships among these elements are bidirectional, with feedback loop from value to EU.

Figure 4: Causality in DTV

On the other hand, the causal relationships in the static notion of value within Jevons’s UTV can be illustrated as shown in Figure 5. From the figure, a unidirectional causal structure starting from “Pleasure” can be observed. Compared to DTV, it becomes clear that the causal link from “Value ≅ Price” to “Preference”—which is a counterpart to PoA—is absent. This difference arises from the elimination of exchangeability at the end of each period. In this case, the optimal strategy for the individual is nothing more than comparing the pleasure or utility inherent in a commodity: this is represented in the figure as “Pleasure ≅ Preference ≅ Utility.”

Figure 5: Causality in UTV

¹⁶In the figure, the symbol (\cong) linking two elements implies that they are essentially equivalent. PoG can be viewed as essentially equivalent to EU, since EU function serves as a representation of PoG. Similarly, in economic tradition, the value of a commodity is defined by its exchange ratio, or relative price, and hence there is no essential distinction between value and price.

It becomes increasingly difficult to make a distinction between the two intangible concepts—EU and value—because people tend to hold the mistaken belief that utility and value reside inherently in commodities, and their EU roughly corresponds to market prices. Consequently, in a highly monetized economy, people inevitably come to believe that the market system measures the latent benefits and pleasures inherent in commodities. This fallacy is further reinforced by the fact that the same term 'value' (used here in a non-economic sense) is conventionally used for two distinct meanings: EU and value. The difference between the two is at best recognized only at the level of an individual's vague sense of 'value' versus the quantified value formed as the societal average. As a result, people tend to mistakenly adopt a unidirectional view in which individual evaluations of commodities determine market prices.

The pervasive acceptance of UTV in mainstream economics appears to be closely related to the cognitive mechanism outlined above. Static views of value are embedded in people's subconscious even before they learn economics.

3.7 The Water-Diamond Paradox

Based on the preceding discussion, the well-known “water-diamond paradox” can be addressed from the perspective of DTV. This paradox raises fundamental questions about the theory of value, and Adam Smith's discussion is particularly well known:

Nothing is more useful than water: but it will purchase scarce any thing; scarce any thing can be had in exchange for it. A diamond, on the contrary, has scarce any value in use; but a very great quantity of other goods may frequently be had in exchange for it. (Smith 1904 [1776], p. 53)

At the root of this paradox lies the assumption that the price of goods reflects some kind of *significance*—commonly called value. The paradox can be restated as a question: what is the source of value? The point at issue was not entirely clear for the ambiguity of the term “value”; nevertheless, the following conditions seem to have been presupposed concerning significance.

- i) The significance of goods can be defined based on its characteristics.
- ii) It can account for the fact that goods with higher significance are associated with higher production costs.
- iii) It can account for the fact that consumers are willing to pay higher prices for goods with higher significance.
- iv) The significance of goods is quantifiable and is reflected in its price.

Advocates of both LTV and UTV have made considerable efforts to ensure the consistency of conditions (i)-(iv). However, as discussed below, each theory still faces unresolved issues.

According to LTV, the significance of goods is understood as the amount of labor necessary for obtaining it. As Adam Smith explains:

If among a nation of hunters, for example, it usually costs twice the labour to kill a beaver which it does to kill a deer, one beaver should naturally exchange for or be worth two deer. (Smith 1904 [1776], p. 67)

LTV successfully accounts for conditions (i) and (ii). In addition, if a barter society is assumed, conditions (iii) and (iv) would also have been satisfied. However, in a capitalist society with advanced specialization, LTV found it difficult to satisfy conditions (iii) and (iv). With respect to condition (iii), consumers can hardly estimate the labor time required to produce given goods in a highly developed society. More importantly, consumers are hardly able to self-produce the same goods available on the market, so that they lack a rational basis for comparing goods in terms of labor time. The problem regarding condition (iv) was even more critical. If labor is the source of value and is reflected in price, one would expect the amount of labor to be proportional to price. However, in a capitalist society, prices comprise not only labor input but also the costs of capital equipment and profit, and therefore a simple proportionality between labor and price is not observed. Proponents of LTV, including Smith, Ricardo, and Marx, struggled to resolve this issue; however, the logical inconsistencies—most notably the transformation problem in the surplus labor theory of value—remain unresolved to this day.

On the other hand, UTV advocates that significance of goods is regarded as its MU. For instance, while water is indispensable for survival, its MU is low because an adequate amount of water is available for everyday needs. In contrast, diamonds possess a high MU due to their scarcity. While UTV works well for conditions (i) and (iii), it provides limited explanations for conditions (ii) and (iv). In terms of condition (ii), it is hardly convincing that utility—merely a subjective concept perceived by individuals—can be assumed to be differentiable with reasonable accuracy, and that the resulting marginal utility is proportional to production costs that are objectively measurable. With respect to condition (iv), UTV has little empirical support because the utility perceived by humans is hard to measure. Furthermore, the theory includes element that seems to contradict common sense. For example, when purchasing groceries, consumers typically purchase an amount sufficient to satisfy their appetite. Under a strict application of marginal utility theory, the MU of groceries would correspond to the utility derived from the very last bite before satisfaction, which should be close to zero. Therefore, according to UTV, groceries ought to be traded at a price nearly equivalent to zero. However, prices are quite unlikely to fall to such a low level in reality.

Thus, both theories of value have reached the present with unresolved deficiencies. Against this background, numerous heterodox economists have abandoned the pursuit of conditions (i)-(iv) and given up the approach of constructing theories on the basis of value theory. While this shift has encouraged pluralism in economics, it has also made the construction of coherent theoretical building blocks more difficult.

The framework of DTV allows for a coherent explanation of conditions (i)-(iv). From the preceding discussion, it becomes clear that the significance of goods is to be identified with the EU (condition (i)). By definition, it is almost evident that consumers are willing to pay higher prices for goods with greater EU (condition (iii)).¹⁷ If a certain goods is to be purchased by a consumer, its EU must be equal to its price (condition (iv)). Since prices are mainly composed of production costs, it necessarily follows that EU nearly corresponds to production costs as well (condition (ii)).

From the perspective of DTV, the water-diamond paradox can be addressed as follows. In a market economy, the reason that water is valued lower than diamonds, despite being essential for survival, is that the effort and cost required to obtain it are low due to its low price. Put simply, the direct source of value is price. It is likely to appear peculiar to most people, as this argument seems to involve circular reasoning. However, from the standpoint that market transactions are negotiations between consumers and firms, this view may appear more natural. This is because price can be interpreted as a visible “transaction threshold” from the firm’s perspective, whereas the EU function held by the consumers constitutes an invisible “transaction threshold” from the consumer’s perspective. In this sense, the distinction between the two is only a matter of whether the threshold is numerically observable; in essence, they are equivalent. Such mutual influence on strategies is also evident in games such as rock-paper-scissors and poker. Thus, the proposition that price constitutes the direct source of value is justified, despite appearing counterintuitive.

Such relationships are inherently difficult to perceive. Yet, without recognizing the mutual influence between ‘value’ in the sense of EU and value that is expressed in price, we cannot achieve an accurate theory of value. The reason that all existing value theories contain inconsistencies is that they have fallen into the fallacy of isolating the significance of goods from the market and treating the structure unidirectionally.

4 Exchange Theory in Dynamic Model

In this section, we aim to examine the effectiveness of DTV introduced in the previous section. We develop a dynamic extension of Jevons’s marginal utility analysis and apply the new method to two types of markets characterized by continuous transactions. We then examine how the resulting outcomes differ from static analysis. The first model examines a barter economy, following Jevons’s analysis, and shows that results analogous to those of UTV can be obtained. The second model incorporates monetary market exchanges, which were not considered in Jevons’s analysis, and demonstrates that the resulting outcomes converge more closely with heterodox schools.

4.1 Marginal Expected Utility Analysis

Within his static framework, Jevons examined the optimal strategies of economic agents by analyzing the relationship between the quantities exchanged and the MU of two commodi-

¹⁷As discussed on page 18, EU does not provide an exact measure of how much one is willing to pay. Nevertheless, it can serve as a close approximation in most cases.

ties. In the dynamic model, where the criterion for choosing a commodity is replaced from utility to EU, it is natural to devise a concept analogous to MU. We define this concept, referred to as "marginal expected utility" (MEU), as follows:

Definition 4.1 (Marginal Expected Utility). *Marginal expected utility (MEU) function* is a quasi-expected utility function under the constraint that a particular transaction frequency is fixed. The output value of the function is called *marginal expected utility (MEU)*.

For clarity, the selected goods are supplied only once, not periodically.

MEU can be regarded as a threshold for determining whether to increase or decrease the frequency of market transactions. For instance, consider a barter market in which 1 kg of meat is exchanged for 10 kg of corn in a single transaction. Let the MEU of 1 kg of meat with respect to corn from the perspective of agent X be given as Table 1.

Table 1: MEU of 1kg of meat with respect to corn.

Trans. frequency (per day)	0 times	1 time	2 times	3 times	4 times
MEU of 1 kg meat (w.r.t corn)	13 kg	12 kg	11 kg	10 kg	9 kg

Suppose that X is a corn farmer and currently engages in two transactions per day to exchange corn for meat. According to Table 1, under the condition that the transaction frequency is fixed, the EU of 1 kg of meat is equal to that of 11 kg of corn. Since the MEU of 1 kg of meat (11 kg of corn) exceeds the market exchange ratio (10 kg of corn), it is rational for X to increase his current transaction frequency. Conversely, if X's current transaction frequency is four times per day, the MEU of 1 kg of meat (9 kg of corn) falls below the market exchange ratio (10 kg of corn), making it rational for X to decrease his transaction frequency. Taken together, these observations imply that X's optimal transaction frequency converges to the point at which the MEU of acquiring commodity with respect to relinquishing one *almost* equals the market exchange ratio.

In order for the preceding argument to be valid, further conditions must be introduced beyond the assumptions made in Section 3. As noted in Section 3.3, a distinction exists between the decision of whether to pay commodity B to obtain commodity A and the decision of which commodities, A or B, to acquire. In other words, $A \sim_S B$ is only equivalent to $\mathbf{0} \sim_{S_A} (B - A)$, and the above discussion ignores the distinction between \sim_S and \sim_{S_A} . Consequently, a small deviation arises between the MEU and the market exchange ratio. Moreover, the above arguments do not take into account the dynamic changes in the economy over time. Therefore, it is necessary to approximate the economy as being stationary. Finally, the state of the market is assumed to be predictable as a function of transaction frequency, which appears to be at odds with the agnostic stance of the DTV framework. On this basis, the following additional assumptions are imposed for the application of MEU analysis.

Assumption 4.2 (Requirements of MEU Analysis). When applying MEU analysis, the market system is assumed to satisfy the following properties:

- The quantity of goods exchanged per transaction is sufficiently small, and the PoA of each agent is almost unchanged with the infinitesimal changes in their holdings. Formally, $\lesssim_s \approx \lesssim_{s_A}$ as $|A| \rightarrow 0$.¹⁸
- The state of the market system, as well as the PoA of market participants, are approximately stationary throughout the period.
- Given a fixed transaction frequency in the market, the state of the economic system, as well as the PoA of market participants, are *almost* uniquely determined.

In reality, it must be acknowledged that some markets do not meet the above conditions. For infrequently purchased goods, such as housing or private vehicles, the deviation between \lesssim_s and \lesssim_{s_A} is not negligible. In addition, markets for speculative assets, such as stocks and Bitcoin, cannot be considered stationary. Those markets are deemed unsuitable for the application of MEU analysis and are thus excluded from the remainder of this paper. Regarding the third condition, the possible states of the market under a fixed transaction frequency are considered to be distributed within a region around a central point. Nonetheless, the market is expected to exhibit certain tendencies as a whole, and overall accurate conclusions should be attainable as long as these tendencies are correctly captured.

Let us now consider a visual representation of the above discussion. The MEU of the two commodities exchanged in a single transaction can be illustrated as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: MEU curves of meat and corn

The horizontal axis represents the transaction frequency per day. The vertical axis indicates the MEU of the commodities exchanged using 1 kg of corn as the *numeraire*, which

¹⁸Since no mathematical definition of the 'closeness' between PoA has been provided, the notation $\lesssim_s \approx \lesssim_{s_A}$ lacks a precise meaning. However, this assumption is generally regarded as self-evident in economic literature and has rarely been questioned. As it is also consistent with common intuition, we therefore proceed without a rigorous definition of this 'closeness'.

need not be identical to either of the commodities exchanged. As discussed earlier, the transaction frequency converges to the point where the MEU of acquiring commodity in terms of relinquishing commodity nearly coincides to their exchange ratio. This condition is equivalent to the equality of their MEU when evaluated in terms of arbitrary goods—for example, 1 kg of corn—as the *numeraire*. Hence, in Figure 6, the transaction frequency desired by X is determined at the intersection of the two MEU curves. By analogy with Jevons’s *marginal utility (MU) analysis*, this approach may be referred to as the *marginal expected utility (MEU) analysis*.

4.2 Dynamic Analysis of Barter Market

By applying MEU analysis, we are able to analyze Jevons’s barter model in a dynamic setting. The following adjustments are made to the assumptions of Jevons’s static model.

- Trading bodies X and Y produce commodities A and B, respectively, with a constant frequency.
- X and Y engage in market transactions at a constant frequency.
- When scaled by commodity C as the *numeraire*, the MEU of a commodity follows the law of *diminishing marginal “expected” utility*; that is, the incentive to trade declines as the frequency of transaction increases.

The following results are obtained, which are almost the same as those of static analysis except for the addition of “expected.”

- (i) In a state of market disequilibrium, price adjustments occur towards equilibrium.
- (ii) In a state of market equilibrium, the exchange ratio between the two commodities is determined by the ratio of their marginal *expected* utility.

The derivation steps are similar. Suppose, for the sake of argument, that the exchange ratio is fixed. According to the law of diminishing marginal expected utility, the MEU curves of commodities A and B in terms of commodity C are obtained as upward- and downward-sloping curves, respectively (see Figure 7). The intersection in the left-hand figure represents X’s desired transaction frequency, while that in the right side corresponds to Y’s desired transaction frequency.

When X and Y have different desired transaction frequency, the one who cannot attain their desired frequency will attempt to increase it by accepting a less favorable exchange ratio. As illustrated in Figure 8, this activates the price adjustment mechanism described in Statement (i). In market equilibrium, both agents’ desired frequency are fulfilled, and the market price must correspond to the ratio of MEU (Statement (ii)).

Thus, in a two-commodities barter model, the static and dynamic structures exhibit no essential differences.

Figure 7: Barter market with continuous exchanges

Figure 8: Mechanism of market price adjustment with continuous exchanges

4.3 Dynamic Analysis of Money-Mediated Market

We then analyze a more realistic commodity market, in which money is used as a medium of exchange, based on the following assumptions:

- Consumers are willing to obtain commodities by paying money, while firms are willing to obtain money by selling their commodities.
- Consumers purchase commodities for their own use without considering future exchange.
- Consumers engage in transactions continuously at a constant frequency.
- The demand for commodities obeys the law of diminishing marginal expected utility.
- Each firm sets price independently so as to secure positive profits. The law of one price is not explicitly assumed, and price bargaining does not occur in each transaction.
- Firms own fixed capital with sufficient production capacity and operate under constant unit variable costs (UVC) regardless of scale.
- Firms aim to keep their inventories constant by reproducing the same quantity immediately after a sale.

- All commodities are assumed to be homogeneous.
- Market participants are heterogeneous. Variations are acknowledged in consumers' money holdings and consumption propensities, as well as in firms' UVC.
- Money is modeled as fiat currency lacking intrinsic utility. The reason for its broad acceptance is not examined here and is taken as an empirical premise.

In static models, money is more difficult to handle than commodities due to the lack of intrinsic utility. In dynamic models, however, money is more tractable, as its EU derives solely from the exchangeability.

From the firm's perspective, the MEU curves of money and commodity are depicted by the two horizontal lines as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Firm's MEU curves of money and commodity

The horizontal axis represents the transaction frequency per day, while the vertical axis measures the MEU in monetary terms. Unless otherwise noted, magnitude of EU and MEU are henceforth expressed in monetary units. Obviously, the MEU of money obtained from a sale always equals the market price. Given the firm's strategy of keeping inventory constant, UVC are incurred to replace each unit sold. As a result, the MEU of the commodity equals its UVC and, by assumption, remains constant regardless of the transaction frequency.¹⁹

In Figure 9, the MEU curve of money is tentatively drawn above that of commodity; however, it should be noted that relative positions of the two curves has not been determined yet. All we know, at this point, is that both curves are horizontal. Hereafter, we analyze the price-setting strategy of firms. A firm's profit can be expressed by the following accounting identity:

$$\text{Profit} = \text{Price} \times \text{Qty} - (\text{UVC} \times \text{Qty} + \text{FixedCosts})$$

¹⁹The MEU derived from a sale is not equivalent to the marginal cost, despite nearly identical role. The definition of marginal cost implicitly pertains to infinitesimal changes in production frequency. Whereas MEU is defined under the assumption of a single recipient of goods throughout the whole period, which does not alter the frequency of production on average.

where $\text{Price} \times \text{Qty}$ corresponds to total sales, while $\text{UVC} \times \text{Qty}$ coincides to total variable costs. Letting $\text{UFC} = \text{FixedCosts}/\text{Qty}$, the above equation can be rewritten as:

$$\text{Price} = \text{UVC} + \text{UFC} + \frac{\text{Profit}}{\text{Qty}}$$

$\text{UFC} > 0$ holds as firms own fixed capital, and by the assumption of positive profits, $\text{Profit} > 0$ follows as well. Hence, it follows that the price exceeds the UVC by a certain margin. Returning to Figure 9, it becomes clear that the MEU of the money obtained from a sale (i.e., the price) must exceed that of the commodity sold (i.e., the UVC), implying that the two MEU curves do not intersect. Given unlimited production capacity, firms are both willing and able to satisfy consumers' demands at any level. Accordingly, in terms of production amount, firms always follow a passive strategy of responding to consumers' demands.

We now further analyze the firm's price-setting strategy from the perspective of survival among competitors. Since the consumer's sensitivity to the price change is subjective and hard to estimate, the mathematical formulation of the exact price level is not trivial. Even so, qualitative analysis is still possible. Let *required profit* denote the minimum level of profit that justifies the firm to remain in the market. The firm's minimum acceptable price is therefore given by:

$$\text{Price} > (\text{UVC} + \text{UFC}) + \frac{\text{RequiredProfit}}{\text{Qty}}$$

We examine firm's price-setting strategy under two cases of consumer price sensitivity.

- **Ideal case:** Consider an hypothetical market in which consumers invariably choose the lower-priced commodity, even when the price difference is minimal. Cartels or collusive behavior are excluded from consideration. Under these conditions, the law of one price naturally holds. If multiple firms are selling at the prevailing market price, a slight price reduction becomes a profitable strategy by attracting customers away from competitors. Consequently, price-cutting competition arises, thereby prompting firms to lower their prices as long as the required profit remains attainable. Firms that fall into deficit will be eliminated from the market. This process continues until the last firm, which sets the lowest price, remains in the market. At this point, the market price has fallen to the level consistent with the minimum acceptable price of the last-eliminated firm. The remaining firm refrains from raising prices to maintain its monopoly, while the absence of competitors provides little incentive to lower prices. As a result, the market price stabilizes around that level.
- **Realistic case:** In reality, consumers do not always prefer the commodities with the lowest price. For instance, purchasing a more expensive item from a nearby

store may be practically rational, and factors such as quality, brand, and trustworthiness influence consumer choice. These elements alleviate the downward pressure on prices. Moreover, existence of cartels and collusion will push prices upward. Therefore, in more realistic case, the price-cutting competition will be less intensive, allowing more firms to survive and resulting in a market price that exceeds the level predicted in the idealized case.

In summary, under idealized conditions where the market competition functions most effectively, the market price settles at the level corresponding the second-lowest value of minimum acceptable price among firms. When various external factors are taken into account, there is upward pressure on prices. It is difficult to quantify the magnitude of this effect, and no further analysis is pursued in the present paper. However, the above discussion suggests that the basic pricing strategy for firms is to set prices to ensure a markup that exceeds the required profit per unit, in addition to covering production costs (UVC + UFC).

We then turn to the analysis of consumer's optimal strategy. The MEU of both money and commodity are illustrated as shown in Figure 10:

Figure 10: Consumer's MEU curves of money and commodity

Due to the law of diminishing marginal expected utility, the MEU curve of commodity slopes downward. In contrast, the MEU of the money used for payment, which corresponds to the price, forms a horizontal line. Consequently, the two MEU curves intersect at a single point, which determines the consumer's desired transaction frequency.²⁰

It is important to note that the downward-sloping MEU curves in Figure 10 rest on the assumption that the consumer has no alternative means to satisfy their needs. For instance, suppose the commodity of interest is Company A's bottled water, purchased solely to satisfy thirst. If another market offers Company B's bottled water with identical taste, volume, and market price, the MEU curve of the commodity would no longer exhibit a downward slope as shown in Figure 10. The reason is that, even if no transactions are engaged for Company A's bottled water, a consumer can substitute it with Company B's

²⁰Strictly speaking, downward-sloping of the MEU curve of commodity does not necessarily intersect with the MEU curve of money as the slope gradually flattens. Nonetheless, such situation suggests that the consumer would spend their entire budget to purchase the commodities, which is not feasible in reality.

bottled water, and thus have no incentive to pay more than the prevailing market price to obtain Company A's bottled water. Consequently, the MEU curve for Company A's bottled water partially aligns with that of money as illustrated in Figure 11, and the intersection between the two curves is not uniquely determined. Accordingly, the market shares of Company A and B are undetermined. If several commodities can fulfill the same needs, the optimal purchasing strategy cannot be uniquely determined.

Figure 11: Consumer's MEU: Competitive case

To summarize the analysis of the dynamic exchange model between money and producible commodities, the transaction frequency is determined by the consumers' demand. Ideally, firms set the market prices at approximately $UVC + UFC + (\text{required profit}/Q_{ty})$, and slightly higher when frictions are present. Firms never withhold supply of their commodities, since selling is invariably profitable. Our analysis reveals that the most fundamental economic principle—that price is determined at the point where supply equals demand, as implied by static models—does not apply to the more realistic exchange model that incorporates money. Therefore, market can equilibrate at a "disequilibrium" price.

4.4 Discussion

In this section, we have analyzed two models: a barter model and a money-mediated exchange model. In the barter model, it has been shown that the optimal exchange ratio corresponds to the ratio of marginal "expected" utilities, resulting in an equilibrium between supply and demand. This outcome is broadly consistent with mainstream claims based on static analysis. When money is incorporated, however, the firm's MEU of selling commodity and obtaining money cannot be identical, thereby leading to a disequilibrium between supply and demand.

The market disequilibrium derived in the money-mediated market model presented in this section is closely aligned with the Post-Keynesian market theory, as represented by Keynes, Kalecki, and Robinson. In particular, the underlying assumptions—such as excess production capacity and constant unit cost—and our claim that market prices are settled at the level of production costs ($UVC + UFC$) plus a markup ($>$ required profit per unit) share many features with Kalecki's work, despite minor differences in detail (Kalecki 1971, pp. 43–45). However, regarding the causes of market disequilibrium, the position taken in this study departs from Post-Keynesian thoughts. Although various explanations have been proposed within the Post-Keynesian school, it is often the case—most

notably in Robinson’s argument—that the cause of disequilibrium markets is attributed to the oligopolistic nature of firms (Robinson 1933). Robinson’s argument focuses on the problem that Marshall’s explanation of market mechanisms conflicted with empirical evidence. In Marshallian theory, market equilibrium under perfect competition presupposes that firms are subject to diminishing returns in production; otherwise, the most profitable strategy for a firm would be to expand output indefinitely. However, numerous surveys indicate that the majority of firms exhibit constant or increasing returns to scale, highlighting the clear discrepancy between theory and reality, as noted by Sraffa and Keen (Sraffa 1926; Keen 2011). Robinson’s theory of imperfect competition was developed to address such limitations inherent in perfect competition market models.

We concur with the Post-Keynesian critique that the mainstream economic theory of market prices is fundamentally problematic due to the reliance on the unrealistic assumption of diminishing return. However, their explanation attributing the nature of disequilibrium to market oligopoly is questionable, since many actual markets appear to be adequately competitive. For instance, there exist numerous commodities, such as groceries and general merchandise, which do not require advanced production techniques. The barriers to entry in these markets are relatively low, and oligopolistic characteristics are hardly observed. Even in such markets, no firm follows the convention of expanding production until marginal cost meets price, and instead generally adopts strategies that adjust supply in accordance with demand (Sraffa 1926, p. 543).

According to our money-mediated market model, the fundamental cause of market disequilibrium lies in the asymmetry between consumers and firms. From the consumer’s perspective, the MEU curves of the two goods have an intersection. In contrast, from the firm’s perspective, both curves are horizontal and thus do not intersect. This discrepancy arises because consumers acquire commodities for personal consumption, which exhibits downward-sloping MEU curve, whereas firms acquire commodities for the purpose of exchange, resulting in a constant MEU regardless of transaction frequency. The MEU analysis presented in this section resolves both issues: inapplicability of diminishing returns, and the widespread existence of competitive markets. In our analysis, output is determined by consumer demand under the assumption of constant returns to scale. Additionally, the assumption of an ideal market with price competition allows for application to perfect competition markets as well.

Given the above considerations, the economic definition of the term “perfect competition market” is inappropriate within the framework of DTV. Traditionally, an equilibrium state in which supply equals demand has been considered a requirement for a perfect competition market. In our view, however, market competitiveness must be distinguished from the equilibrium of supply and demand. This is because markets that are sufficiently competitive in the usual sense can equilibrate at a point of disequilibrium in which demand determines supply, as demonstrated in the money-mediated model.

The findings obtained under DTV framework diverge significantly from those of conventional economic theory, primarily due to the explicit modeling of transaction continuity.

By incorporating the temporal continuity of exchange, MEU analysis allows for a proper treatment of money—an issue that remains difficult within the general equilibrium model. In comparison with the general equilibrium model, the dynamic model presented here provides a more realistic depiction of market behavior.

It is important to carefully examine the outcomes resulting from the simplifying assumptions adopted in our analysis. In particular, we have simplified the shapes of the MEU curves, assuming them to be upward-sloping, downward-sloping, or horizontal. These simplifications were intended to facilitate explanation by showing simpler graphs; however, the actual curves are likely to be more complex. Taking this into consideration, the MEU curves could possess multiple intersections rather than a unique one under more realistic conditions. Furthermore, when the interactions among multiple markets are considered, the existence of market prices that simultaneously clears all markets is not guaranteed, as has long been recognized in general equilibrium analysis. Accordingly, the uniqueness and the convergence of market prices are beyond the scope of our claims. Instead, the present analysis focuses on the direction of market price adjustment, which differs between barter market and money-mediated market. In other words, barter market adjusts exchange ratios to resolve discrepancy between supply and demand, whereas in money-mediated market, no such mechanism exists. The reason is that, provided the relation “price > UVC” holds, the EU ‘obtained’ from sale (price) will never fall below the EU ‘lost’ by selling (UVC) from the firm’s perspective. This is fundamental principle for firms to secure profit regardless of the shapes of the MEU curves. Therefore, the aforementioned assumptions do not undermine our essential conclusion.

It is also worthwhile to note the pricing mechanism. The conventional market equilibrium theory assumes that prices are set by a hypothetical auction system, and firms act as price takers. Admittedly, the price range available to a firm is practically constrained by competitors’ pricing. Nonetheless, it is a well-known fact that firms independently set their prices, and modeling them as price takers may fail to capture market realities. In fact, mainstream’s premise of an auction system arose from its static approach. In Jevons’s static analysis, money is excluded—presumably due to the intractability of money that lacks intrinsic utility—and barter exchange is examined instead. In this case, since the exchanges are conducted between commodities, any asymmetry between supply and demand is excluded, and an image of a symmetric equilibrium market follows as a logical necessity. Therefore, the introduction of a hypothetical auction system is required to preserve the symmetric relationship. As such, the mainstream depiction of equilibrium market originates from the technical limitations of static analysis. In contrast, the dynamic model presented in this section is capable of handling money that possesses only exchange value. Consequently, our model allows for the analysis of commodity-money exchanges under the asymmetric assumption that price-setting power rests exclusively with suppliers.

The assumptions sustaining mainstream economics—such as perfect competition, barter economy, and centralized auction system—have been widely criticized from inside and outside the community. There is little doubt that one of the reasons why mainstream economics has not abandoned them as its core theoretical framework was the incentive

to preserve its paradigm. Yet, another significant reason lies in the widespread acceptance of an intrinsic notion of 'value' that is determined solely by the properties and scarcity of commodities and is independent of market institutions. By acknowledging this notion of 'value', one could argue that analyzing highly hypothetical market models—where realistic institutions are abstracted away, as mathematical economists have done—is worthwhile. However, as discussed in the previous section, such an intrinsic notion of 'value' is merely a fallacy ingrained in everyday thinking. In other words, a valid notion of 'value' (i.e., EU) must reflect its reciprocal relationship with markets, and thus exchange ratios vary entirely depending on the institutional structure of the market. In light of this, it becomes evident that mainstream exchange theory, which abstracts away realistic market institutions in its formal models, faces significant difficulty in capturing actual market mechanisms.

5 Tax-Driven Money: Mechanism of Monetary Circulation

We continue to examine the validity of DTV framework in this section. By applying MEU analysis to the role of government in a market economy, we assess its theoretical compatibility with the arguments advanced by MMT. According to MMT, money is accepted because it serves as a means of tax payment and further claims that the value of money is regulated by what is required to obtain the currency to fulfill tax obligations:

MMT has typically argued that money's value is determined by what one must do to obtain the currency that can be used to discharge the tax liability. (Wray 2024, p. 29)

That is, the role of state authority is emphasized in the process through which money acquires value and circulates within markets. This perspective is summarized as "tax-driven money view," and several studies have presented verbal models that illustrate this view (Wray 1999, pp. 155–176; Mosler 2023, pp. 87–92; Wray 2024b, pp. 27–34). However, these discussions rely primarily on natural language and are not regarded as formal models. Consequently, the assumptions and premises concerning individual behavior in MMT's verbal models remain ambiguous.

This section attempts to provide a more precise description of the tax-driven money view through the lens of DTV. As a caveat, the objective here is not to provide a faithful historical description of evolution of economic systems, but rather to pursue the logical clarity and to examine the validity of DTV proposed in this study. Moreover, the analysis presented here involves certain premises that differ from those in earlier MMT literature.

5.1 Self-Sufficient Individuals and Government Model

We first analyze the simplest form of the economic system. In this model, following assumptions are made.

- The economy consists of a fixed number of citizens and a single government authority.
- Each citizen sustains a self-sufficient livelihood based on the resources of their own land, and private transactions are entirely absent.
- The government levies a monthly head tax of T yen on each citizen. Failure to pay the full amount results in a penalty proportional to the shortfall, prompting individuals to organize their activities so as to avoid incurring such penalties.
- All currency required to fulfill tax obligations originates exclusively from government spending.
- The government provides unconditional employment to all citizens who wish to work, with wages set uniformly at W yen per hour.
- Citizens may accumulate currency in anticipation of future tax obligations; however, their savings are subject to an upper bound, and once this limit is reached, they reduce their services to the government so as to avoid unnecessary effort.

We also apply the MEU analysis to the present model. Considering labor as a type of goods, the employment relationship between citizens and the government can be interpreted as a market transaction exchanging labor for wage. The MEU of labor and wage in monetary terms from citizen's viewpoint are illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Citizen's MEU curves of labor and wage

The point where the curve rises vertically corresponds to the minimum frequency of service provision required to fulfill the tax obligations. Below this threshold, a citizen is incapable of consistently meeting their duties and thus cannot avoid penalties, whereby forcing them to desire more currency in exchange for labor to mitigate punishment. In this situation, the MEU of labor falls below the government wage, leading the citizen to increase the provision of their services. Conversely, if a citizen sustains a frequency of labor provision beyond the required threshold, they have no incentive to obtain extra currency in exchange for labor. The reason is that their current frequency of service provision is already sufficient to meet future tax obligations, and no alternative use for the currency exists. Hence, the MEU of labor becomes infinite ($+\infty$), exceeding that of government wage, which drives the citizen to decrease the provision of their services.

In this way, an adjustment process operates so that the frequency of citizen's service provision converges to the level required for tax payments. As a consequence, the long-term balance of government expenditure (i.e., tax income minus spending) converges to zero. This outcome, however, is at odds with the MMT claim that ongoing fiscal deficit is the desirable state of government expenditure. This difference originates from the simplifying assumption that the tax obligation, the government wage, and the population are held constant. In a scenario where these nominal magnitudes continue to rise, the total savings held by citizens would also expand continuously, thereby making it possible to sustain permanent fiscal deficits. Despite being deviated from the MMT argument, the following analysis assumes constant nominal values for the sake of simplicity.

5.2 Consideration of Private Transaction

In the previous model, interactions among citizens were entirely absent. Over time, however, it is plausible that rational citizens would come to recognize the potential use of currency in exchanges among them. A citizen who possesses surplus currency may propose a transaction to another citizen who faces a shortage. The former gains some benefit in exchange for currency, whereas the latter reduces their services to the government. Accordingly, the transaction is mutually beneficial. To analyze the mechanism of occurring such transactions, let us consider a simplified private economy. In this setting, it is assumed that there exist two citizen groups, X and Y, with distinct characteristics.

Citizen group X owns fertile land and is able to produce sufficient crops for subsistence. As a result, X often cannot consume the entire crops and frequently disposes of the surplus ones. Conversely, citizen group Y possesses infertile land, resulting in less amount of production of crops that is chronically insufficient for subsistence. X seeks to make effective use of surplus crops, while Y requires additional crops. As a result, a mutually advantageous exchange of crops for currency arises, spontaneously leading to the formation of a market system that facilitates such transactions.

Although transactions of crops in a real market are influenced by multiple factors including demand-supply balance and the price formation mechanism, the present analysis adopts the following simplified setting: the market price is fixed at P yen, and the supply of crops exceeds the demand—an outcome derived from the money-mediated market model. Given these conditions, the MEU analysis is applied to the model.

From the perspective of X, the first priority is to secure the crops necessary for personal subsistence, and then X attempts to sell all surplus production. Since the currency obtained from these sales can be used to satisfy tax obligations, X can reduce the labor services to the government accordingly. Thus, the MEU of labor and wage from X's perspective changes as shown in Figure 13, compared to the previous model that lacks private transactions.

Because of the income from private transactions, the frequency of labor services required for X to meet tax obligations decreases, shifting the vertical line in the figure leftward. The magnitude of this change is governed by the price P , the amount of surplus production, and effective demand. In some cases, the income from private transactions may suffice to

Figure 13: X's MEU curves of labor and wage

cover tax obligations entirely, resulting in no need for X to supply labor to the government.

Considering Y's perspective, in order to compensate for the shortfall in crops through market transactions, Y must supply labor to the government beyond the level required for tax obligations, thereby earning additional income. The MEU of labor from Y's perspective changes as shown below:

Figure 14: Y's MEU curves of labor and wage

The segment ascending in the upper-right direction represents the situation in which Y faces a trade-off between supplying additional labor to the government and accepting a shortage of crops. As appetite gradually diminishes, the marginal satisfaction derived from additional crops declines. Depending on government wages or market prices, Y may choose to limit the amount of labor supplied, accepting a state in which appetite is not fully satisfied. Once the frequency of labor provision reaches to the level at which Y's appetite is fully satisfied, no further incentive remains to supply additional labor in return for currency, resulting in infinite MEU of labor ($+\infty$).

The trade-off for Y can also be illustrated through an examination of Y's strategy in the private market. By fixing the transaction frequency in the private market, the MEU diagram of currency and crops denominated in terms of labor is shown in Figure 15. Here, the labor-denominated MEU serves as an indicator of the amount of labor one can afford for acquiring the goods.

Since the amount of labor required to obtain currency per unit transaction (i.e., price) is constant at P/W , the MEU curve of currency is depicted by a horizontal line. On the other

Figure 15: Y's MEU curves of currency and crop

hand, the satisfaction derived from crops declines with additional consumption, and thus the MEU curve of crops slopes downward to the right and falls vertically once appetite is fully satisfied. Y's demand for crops is determined at the intersection of the two curves.

In this way, the analysis demonstrates that private transactions may arise between heterogeneous citizen groups X and Y, and that such interactions can be examined by using MEU analysis. The driving force behind these transactions is the government's taxation authority. In effect, the government can obligate citizens to supply labor services, with currency serving as a measurable token of these services. Furthermore, the portability and impersonal nature of currency enable it to be circulated among citizens. As a result, currency possesses a latent power to influence the behavior of individuals who is hoping to reduce their labor supply to the government. This idea bears a resemblance to LTV in classical economics (Smith 1904 [1776], pp. 54–56).

What would occur if the government were to permanently abolish tax obligations? In that case, as the necessity for currency disappears for X, the decision whether to exchange surplus crops for currency or disposing them would be entirely arbitrary, governed by whim rather than necessity. Therefore, the X's MEU curves of crop and currency would no longer intersect at a unique point, and the frequency of transactions desired by X would become indeterminate. This suggests that, even in the absence of government intervention, the emergence and persistence of private transactions cannot be entirely ruled out within DTV framework. Nevertheless, it is evident that the government's taxation authority plays a pivotal role for encouraging such transactions.

5.3 Consideration of Capital System

We now examine the process by which wage-labor arises. As we have seen in the previous model, the development of the private economy expands the use of currency beyond tax payment. Consequently, the incentive for citizens to hoard currency strengthens, the means of obtaining currency become diversified, and economic inequality emerges inevitably. Those who accumulate enormous wealth may invent a system, the so-called "capital system," that employs others to produce industrial products efficiently, thereby seeking to generate further wealth.

We begin by examining the behavior of capitalists. As discussed in Section 4.3, the price of

a product settles at production costs plus a markup. Capitalists undertake investment when the expected return exceeds the required threshold, which depends on effective demand and the investors' *animal spirits* reflecting their risk tolerance, as Keynes put it. While these elements are hard to formalize mathematically, it is reasonable to expect that changes in private savings influence investment decisions, and that, in turn, capital investment and employment fluctuate accordingly.

We then focus on the behavior of working-class citizens. Consider a citizen who is willing to acquire a particular industrial products. Because of the limited durability of the products, it is necessary to regularly secure a certain quantity of them. To obtain these products, a citizen faces two alternatives: (i) purchasing them on the market or (ii) producing them by their own labor. Suppose that a portion of the required quantity is procured from the market by spending P yen, while the remainder is self-produced requiring labor time L per unit. Under this assumption, the MEU curves in the product market, measured in terms of unit labor, are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Citizen's MEU curves of product and currency

While the market transaction does not meet the required quantity, the MEU of the product corresponds to the labor time L that is required for self-production. In contrast, the MEU of currency equals the labor time required to obtain it, which is expressed as P/W . In the early stage where production efficiency through capital equipment remains low, prices cannot be sufficiently reduced, and the MEU of currency exceeds that of the product (see Figure 16a). At this point, citizens have no incentive to purchase products in the market, resulting in no market transactions. As production becomes more efficient, prices are sufficiently lowered, and the MEU of the product exceeds that of currency. In this case, procuring all products from the market becomes the rational choice. In other words, when the amount of labor required for earning the market price (P/W) is lower than the amount of labor required for self-production (L), it becomes more beneficial to purchase on the market. As the division of labor expands and productivity improves, market purchases become more efficient for various products. This leads to a decline in self-sufficient lifestyles, and wage-labor becomes common.

With the development of the private economy, the demand for employees by firms in-

creases. At this point, a competition for labor arises between the government and the private sector. Under the circumstances that the government provides unlimited employment at a fixed wage, firms must offer wages higher than the government wage to secure workers. Assuming perfect employment fluidity, firms first hire the workers as needed, and the remaining workers are subsequently employed by the government. Seemingly, private employment plays a dominant role, while government employment appears passive. Nevertheless, considering that nominal values, such as wages and tax obligations, are constant and savings are upper bounded, government employment must be consistent with the tax level in the long run, as discussed in Section 5.1. Under these conditions, the following adjustment mechanism operates:

- Continuous growth in savings enhances effective demand, thereby increasing private employment while decreasing government workers, which induces dynamics pushing private savings downward.
- Continuous decline in savings reduces effective demand, thereby decreasing private employment while increasing government workers, which induces dynamics pushing private savings upward.

As such, in the long run, private employment fluctuates passively, with its equilibrium level largely regulated by government policy. Deficit spending by the government generates private savings and plays a role in stabilizing economic fluctuations.

5.4 Discussion

While the previous section applied the MEU analysis to examine private market interactions, this section demonstrates that the same methodology is applicable to analyze interactions between government and citizens.

The conventional marginal utility approach has largely omitted the existence of the state as a currency issuer because of the difficulty of incorporating money. Meanwhile, MMT describes the circular dynamics of the economy through the state's currency issuance model, yet there remains ambiguity regarding individual behavior for the reliance on natural language. Given this context, there has been a prevailing view that mathematical analysis based on rational individuals is incompatible with incorporating social or institutional elements, such as the state and money. However, this section has shown that the alternative methodology presented in this paper enables the analysis of the tax-driven monetary dynamics of MMT, based on the state's authority as well as bounded rationality of individuals. The following conclusions obtained using our methodology are largely in agreement with MMT claims, suggesting that DTV framework is sufficiently compatible with MMT.

- Government taxation of citizens creates a demand for currency (Tymoigne and Wray 2013, pp. 7–8; Mitchell, Wray, and Watts 2019, pp. 376–378).
- The demand for currency may exceed the level required to satisfy immediate tax obligations due to the needs for future taxes and the existence of private transactions

(Mosler 2023, pp. 88–89).

- Government fiscal policy serves as a pricing reference in private markets. That is, the public-sector wage sets a minimum for private-sector wages and functions as a price anchor for market prices (Mitchell, Wray, and Watts 2019, p. 757).
- Even if the government unconditionally hires all unemployed citizens willing to work, this will not lead to the crowding out of employment in the private labor market, assuming perfect labor mobility. Under such a policy, government spending responds countercyclically to economic fluctuations, thereby stabilizing the economy. This corresponds to the policy known as the Job Guarantee Program (JGP) advocated by MMT (Mitchell, Wray, and Watts 2019, p. 760).

As a caveat, given that this section analyzes highly simplified economies, the implications for real-world applications remain uncertain. Future work should focus on enhancing the model's realism.

6 Conclusion

The general equilibrium theory, which constitutes the core of mainstream economics, has long been subject to extensive criticism. Countless issues have been raised, including human irrationality, information asymmetry, price rigidities, the oligopolistic nature of firms, and the rejection of barter economies, among others. Although mainstream economists have made various efforts to address such criticisms, there remains a significant gap between the theory and the real-world market mechanism.

The divergence between general equilibrium theory and real markets has consistently been ascribed, within and beyond the academic community, to the social and irrational aspects of the real economy. A common critique holds that the so-called *failures of economics* arose from its fascination with physics, as evidenced by a scientific orientation and an overreliance on mathematics. Meanwhile, following decades of investigation, the mathematical analysis of the theory is largely considered complete, such that even the most severe critics of economics seldom doubt the presence of technical defects in the analysis.

We aim to contest prevailing views regarding the *failures of economics*. Our perspective is diametrically opposed to conventional views and, to put it succinctly, argues that the static analytical framework of mainstream economics contains a significant logical *flaw* that is responsible for the resulting inconsistencies. That *flaw* originates from the unrealistic assumption: all exchanges are completed simultaneously at certain moments. At first sight, this may seem a minor issue, and it has never been brought up for discussion. However, as shown in this study, the effect of this assumption is not negligible.

Section 3 constructs a novel dynamic framework of value theory through natural deductive reasoning by discarding the preceding assumption. According to the new theory, the perceived significance of goods—commonly called 'value'—is effectively represented by its EU. The most remarkable insight here is that there exists a reciprocal relationship between what we perceive as 'value' and price, yet most people adopt a unidirectional

view in which 'value' is simply reflected in price. This fallacy ultimately arises from our tendency of static worldview and gives rise to various inconsistencies in conventional value theories.

In Section 4, a new analytical method, MEU analysis, is developed as a dynamic extension of the conventional MU analysis. Through this method, we have investigated two forms of dynamic exchange systems—barter market and money-mediated market. In analyzing the former barter case, we have obtained results nearly identical to the conventional MU analysis: market adjusts toward the optimal state in which exchange ratios coincide with MEU ratios, bringing supply and demand into equilibrium. In contrast, in the latter monetary model, it is found that market prices are settled at the level of production costs (UVC + UFC) plus a markup (>required profit per unit), while supply and demand do not equilibrate. This outcome is largely consistent with the traditional price theory of Post-Keynesian school.

In Section 5, the same methodology is applied to the analysis of a state model, illustrating how the state's exercise of taxation authority can account for the emergence of private exchange within a self-sufficient society and the subsequent development of a capitalist system. Despite some remaining ambiguities, it has been demonstrated that, relative to the original argument by MMT proponents, conclusions widely consistent with MMT can be derived through a more explicit specification of individual behavior.

DTV proposed in this study highlights a new approach to the theoretical development of MMT and Post-Keynesian economics. Historically, both schools have constructed their theories without a theory of value, which has resulted in criticisms concerning the lack of microfoundations, the absence of theoretical consistency, and an insufficient mathematical foundation. In response, heterodox economists' criticisms of mainstream economics—for instance, concerning methodological individualism and the overreliance on mathematical modeling (Skidelsky 2022 [2020])—seem to imply defensive intent. Given that traditional value theories were difficult to integrate into their own theoretical frameworks, their decision to abandon the existing value theories may be regarded as a reasonable tradeoff in pursuit of a practical economic theory. However, if the *flaw* of traditional value theories is exposed and a new value theory becomes available, there is no need to be constrained by conventional thoughts.

The argument presented in this paper indicates that the assumption of rational individuals and the mathematical formalism may not constitute the fundamental problem in mainstream economics. Rather, the reliance on static modeling in exchange theory, along with the prevailing notion of intrinsic value, appears to be a more crucial issue underlying these problems. Once this issue is acknowledged, the construction of a comprehensive alternative theory to mainstream economics should become an achievable objective for heterodox economists.

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